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AFTER THE COMPASS AND BEFORE THE CHART: SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON THE ORIGIN OF THE PORTOLAN CHART

GREGORY C. MCINTOSH

The question that frames and directs my inquiry is: After the introduction of the mariner's magnetic compass and before the appearance of the portolan chart, how did a mariner recover his course? How did he plot his course without a map? In other words, in the transitional period between sailing to the eight traditional directions by his eye, without compass, to sailing to 16 and 32 directions by magnetic compass, how did a mariner recover his course *before* the first portolan chart was created and available for use? The course was recovered by solving the triangle, that is, Pythagorean geometry. The three courses are: 1) the intended route, invariably from port of departure to destination port; 2) the actual route, which often deviated from the intended route due to wind and weather; and 3) the recovery route, that is, the route to return toward the intended destination.

From ancient times, mariners in the Mediterranean sailed to the eight winds or eight directions without magnetic compass. The traditional Medieval names for the eight principal winds are: Tramontana (N), Greco (NE), Levante (E), Sirocco (SE), Mecço or Ostro (S), Garbino or Lebicceio (SW), Ponente (W), and Maestro (NW). When out of sight of landmarks and in good weather, by looking at the sun during the day or stars at night, the navigator had a general idea of the directions of the eight winds. Before the mariner's magnetic compass, when sailing to only eight directions, if one had to deviate from the intended course, it was fairly easy to determine the approximate recovery course to get back on the approximate intended course. The navigator worked in roughly 45-degree increments, regardless of the actual unmeasured angle sailed. A mariner did not have to perform any trigonometry to determine his approximate present position or his approximate new course to return to his intended course. To determine the position, keep track of the progress, and plot the course, he did not need maps, geometry, or trigonometry shortcuts. All sailing directions were in terms of the eight directions, that is, 45 degrees to each other.

Even if he sailed to one side or the other of that direction, that is, sailed in a direction between any of the two winds, there were still only eight fundamental directions. No calculations, very simple geometry. Frequent course changes could be solved mentally with the simplest of geometric estimates when the angles are rounded to 45 degree increments. But, of course, the navigating was imprecise and not very accurate. The mariner would sail in an inexact, more general direction, and with some caution and hesitancy. There are indications that when mariners had to sail in a direction in between two

of the eight winds, they resorted to describing them as a little bit to one side or the other of one of the eight winds: "...almost due east but declining a little towards south...", "...southeast but nearer to south...", "...by the southeast and a little east...", "...from the northeast toward the east...", "...a third of a wind from the southwest toward the west...", and many others.¹ These imprecise directions between the eight winds were inexact and approximate.

Before the introduction of the mariner's compass in the Mediterranean, when sailing out of sight of land, a navigator held his course by keeping his wake straight, sighting a star on the horizon or among the rigging, then switching to a different star as the night progressed. But in the daytime, holding a course over an extended period of time was more difficult. He could sail only in a more general direction of each of the eight winds (though an experienced mariner can "sense" the direction).

There are hints of how the compass was initially used by mariners. The earliest references all describe a similar operation: a sliver of loadstone or a needle magnetized by a loadstone was inserted into a piece of straw floating in water. With the compass, the mariner had one more tool and additional method for locating the northern quadrant, and even the direction of north itself, and thus the remaining seven directions. Over time and with experience, mariners learned that the needle *always* reliably pointed to the same apparent point in the north. With the compass, mariners could sail during the daytime when the stars were not visible, across the open sea out of sight of land, or when the sun or stars were obscured by weather. Now ships could sail year around. Trade and commerce increased. And, very significantly, with the more precise measurements of the magnetic compass, mariners could now increase from eight to 16, and then 32, the number of sailing directions they could identify, and the number of directions they could repeatedly point their prows toward.

It is in this transitional period from sailing by the imprecision of eight directions to sailing with the new and more precise mariner's compass, but without the chart, and then to more precise navigating by 16 directions with the compass, but still without the chart, and then later 32 directions—it is in the changing navigation techniques and technologies of this transition that I suggest we must look to find the origin and development of the portolan chart.

If, because of wind and weather, a ship could not sail a direct path to the destination—and as any sailor will tell you,

this is frequently the case—and when sailing by the compass to 16 or 32 directions, to keep track of the progress of the ship toward its destination, determine its position, and plot the course—without the use of charts before the portolan chart was created—the navigator *must* draw the courses. The course was recovered by solving the triangle, that is, Pythagorean geometry. The three courses of the intended route, the actual route, and the recovery route could no longer be mentally manipulated by the navigator as when they were the simple, generalized 45-degree directions of the eight winds. Now they had odd angles, such as 22-1/2 degrees and 11-1/4 degrees, triangles difficult to solve mentally.

One response to the need to calculate the triangles so as to recover the course, was the creation of memorized tables, graphs, and other nomographs and shortcuts, to make this task easier. The first representation of the *marteloio* (Fig. 1), a graphical two-dimensional computation device designed to calculate the triangles, was not until Andrea Bianco's famous portolan atlas of 1436,² but it is referenced in a document in 1390,³ and Ramon Llull described its use aboard a ship in 1295.⁴ But, before the *marteloio* or the chart were created, to plot the course by compass, a navigator would have to draw

traveled, that is, the direction by compass and the actual distance, from the previously plotted point, and the new compass direction and distance to be traversed to recover the course. The three courses form the legs of a triangle. To draw the lines of the three courses, and the triangles thus formed, two other elements are required for the navigator to plot his position and determine

Figure 2. The *Tondo e Quadro* (circle and square), a graphical representation of the *Toleta de Marteloio*, for mariners lacking arithmetic skills. Andrea Bianco atlas of 1436. Venice, Biblioteca Nazionale Marciana, It Z.76 (4783), fol. 1. Wikipedia Commons {{PD-US}}

how to get back on course. One would be a representation of the 16 or 32 directions in which he could sail and was sailing, that is, the directions marked on his compass, a “star” or “rose” of sailing directions of the eight principal winds and the eight half-winds to assist in drawing the triangles with the proper angles. To maintain the proper plotting of the angles of the lines of the triangles, this star-like representation of the 16 or 32 directions would *have* to be drawn on the parchment sheet itself. With eight winds one can do the geometry roughly in one’s head but with the 16 winds or 32 winds of the mariner’s magnetic compass, one *had* to draw the geometric angles.

The other element would be a scale bar or linear scale, that is, a line or bar having a series of marks or graduations at uniform intervals to indicate the ratio and proportion between the dimensions on the sheet of parchment, and the actual distances sailed on the water. (Fig. 3, next page) To draw the triangle made up of the three courses, one must reduce the distances by a uniform ratio. The proportions cannot be hit-or-miss or inconsistent. A scale bar is an absolute necessity. Plotting accurate courses cannot be done without a scale. The scale bar was also drawn onto the same sheet of parchment.

How a navigator would get from one point to the next depended upon the wind. To sail across open water from one point to another, a navigator would draw his intended route. If the wind shifted, as it often does, he would change his tacking as he beat to windward. To each line for a tack, he adds another line to make a right triangle for the calculation. If the ship had to engage in tacking with the bearing repeatedly changing, as was typical in long-distance sailing in open waters, if the navigator had a good idea of his speed and the time

l'anglar	anancia	anancia	retrato	retrato
p. una quarta	20	98	p. 1/4	51
p. do quarta	38	92	p. 2/4	26
p. tre quarta	55	83	p. 3/4	15
p. quatro q.	71	71	p. 4/4	10
p. cinque q.	83	55	p. 5/4	6
p. six quarta	92	38	p. 6/4	4
p. set quarta	98	20	p. 7/4	5 1/10
p. oito quarta	100	00	p. 8/4	8

Figure 1. The *Toleta de Marteloio* is a simple trigonometric table for determining the third side of a right-angle triangle when two sides are known. In the left column are the eight wind directions of one quarter of a 32-point compass. The other columns solve the triangle for the eight directions at distances of 100 miles and 10 miles. Knowing the direction and distance traveled on one side of the triangle, a mariner can use the table and simple arithmetic to determine the new direction and distance to return to his course without resorting to trigonometry. Andrea Bianco atlas of 1436. Venice, Biblioteca Nazionale Marciana, It Z.76 (4783), fol. 1. Wikipedia Commons {{PD-US}} See Fig. 2 for a graphical representation of this chart.

his courses. Sailing by the compass to 16 or more directions but lacking a chart leaves no other option.

Onto his sheet of parchment the medieval mariner would draw the three segments of the route: the originally intended course by compass direction and distance, the course actually

Figure 3. The scale bar and a decorative dragon in the corner of the chart of the Black Sea, Petrus Vesconte atlas of 1318, Cod. 594, fol. 2v-3r. <https://medea.fc.ul.pt/view/chart/2272/viewer>.

traveled, he could determine his present position, based upon his last position, and recover his course. The marine magnetic compass led to an increase in the number of sailing directions and an increase in open-sea sailing. The increase in sailing directions led to the need to draw the three courses. The need to draw the three courses led to using sheets of parchment, eventually one for each of the seven basins of the Mediterranean Sea.⁵ (Fig. 4)

Figure 4. A hypothetical example of recovering the course sailing from Sant Feliu de Guixols, Spain, to Bonifacio, Corsica. AB is the intended course, AC is the actual course sailed, and CD is the return course determined from the *Toleta de Marteloio*. Detail of chart from Petrus Vesconte portolan atlas of 1318, Vienna, Österreichische Nationalbibliothek, Cod. 594, fol. 6v-7r.

From the loadstone sliver to the complete portolan chart, there were many intermediate and incremental steps in improving and refining the accuracy and precision of navigation-

al techniques and the associated equipment – tools created to keep the ship on course or to recover the course. It is my contention that when sailing to the finer, more precise increments of the 16 (and later 32) directions of the new magnetic compass—but before there was a chart—the navigator *must* plot the courses and draw his triangles to the same angles as the compass directions and do so at a scale appropriate to the size of his parchment. This is the essence of the portolan chart. By conveniently combining onto a single piece of parchment his courses and triangles, with a mileage scale to regulate the sizes of the triangles, and a template of the 16 or 32 directions to orient the triangles to the proper angles, the proto-portolan chart was born. The proto-portolan chart did not start out as an image of the Mediterranean Sea or a map. It began as a navigational tool. The portolan chart was the product of a long, evolving process of improvement and refinement of the tools and techniques of the medieval mariner in response to the daily problem facing him: Where am I and how do I get to my destination?

Endnotes

¹ E. G. R. Taylor, *The Haven-Finding Art* (London: Hollis & Carter, 1956), 103; Alessandra Debanne, *Lo Compasso de navigare: Edizione del codice Hamilton 396 con commento linguistico e glossario* (Brussels: Peter Lang, 2011).

² Andrea Bianco and Piero Falchetta, *Atlante Nautico (1436)* (Venice: Arsenale, 1993).

³ Cornelio Desimoni, “Elenco di carte ed atlanti nautici di autore genovese oppure in Genova fatti o conservati,” *Giornale Ligustico 2* (1875), 47: “Nell’Archivio Notarile in Oberto Foglietta, al 12 gennaio 1390, è notato: nell’ inventario de’ beni della madre di Battista de Jacopo un *martelgium* . . . item carta una prò navigando.”

⁴ Ramon Llull, *Arbor Scientiae*, trans. Yanis Damberg (2003), 2:123, at <https://lullianarts.narpan.net/TreeOfScience/TreeOfScience2.pdf> (accessed 5 October 2022).

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